

IN-SITU SYNTHESIS AND INITIAL STRESS MEASUREMENT OF ULTRALONG CARBON NANOTUBE BUNDLES

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Keywords: Carbon nanotube, Initial stress, Resonance Raman spectroscopy

ABSTRACT

Carbon nanotubes are the most promising materials to help us realize the space elevator dream. Additionally, many future applications, such as rackets, ballistic armors and space vehicles also need fibers which are both light and superstrong. Among three kinds of CNTs, horizontal ultralong carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have excellent properties as they have a perfect structure, macroscopic length and controllable orientation. For the promotion of the transformation from micromechanics to macroscopic application of ultralong CNTs, it's significant for us to know whether the ultralong CNT bundles (CNTBs) with perfect structures still have the same excellent mechanical properties as the single ultralong CNT has or not. Herein, we prepared the ultralong CNT bundles (CNTBs) by the controllable gas flow and explored the factors that influence the preparation of the bundles. And the CNTBs with length up to centimeters growing across a slot were in-situ synthesized. For as-grown

horizontal CNT(B)s, we find that there is always an initial stress existed but few studies focus on it. Resonance Raman spectroscopy was used to assess the initial stress of the ultralong carbon nanotubes as inorganic nanoparticles show no influence. It is concluded that the values of the initial stress exist in a pretty wide range and even in a bundle. This can have a big impact on the mechanical properties of ultralong carbon nanotube assemblies.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are the most promising materials to help us realize the space elevator dream. Additionally, many future applications, such as rackets, ballistic armors and space vehicles also need fibers which are both light and superstrong. A single CNT owns a tensile strength over 100 GPa which was demonstrated both theoretically and experimentally. However, it remains a question whether CNTs can still own equivalent strength to single ones when bundled together. Numerous studies have been done to pursue this goal. Some groups sought to spin lots of CNTs into CNT macroscopic fibers. What made us surprised is that the highest tensile strength of CNT fiber achieved was merely about 8.8 GPa with lengths not more than 20 mm. That is because the CNTs they used mostly were vertically aligned or agglomerated CNTs with many defects, impurities, random orientations and discontinuous structures, which may give rise to destructive damage. Irradiated CNT bundles with 200 keV electrons possess a tensile strength of ~17 GPa. SWCNT ropes were measured to own an average breaking strength of 30 GPa though with a gauge length of 1 μm . Nevertheless, they are still far lower than that of individual ones.

Recent breakthroughs have enabled us to synthesize half meter long CNTs with a defect-free and neat structure. As such, ultralong CNT bundles (CNTBs), possessing a strength close to the theoretical value of isolated CNTs, were expected to be fabricated by bundling these perfect ultralong CNTs together. The growth of CNTs obey the “kite mechanism”. As a result,

the growth orientation of CNTs appears to be intensely sensitive to gas flow. Thus, we developed a gas flow focusing (GFF) method based on this sensitivity to in-situ synthesize CNTBs with a defect-free, neat, uniform oriented and continuous structure.

2 METHODS

Synthesis of suspended CNTBs. A solution of FeCl_3 in ethanol (0.03 M) which was used as the catalyst precursor was deposited onto a silicon substrate by micro-printing. Two quartz triangular prisms were placed on the two sides of a silicon substrate as gas barriers to focus the parallel gas flow. A large quartz boat which held the substrate and barriers was put into a horizontal quartz tube with a diameter of 31 mm which was put inside a tube furnace. After reduction in Ar and H_2 (H_2 :Ar = 2:1 by volume, with a total flow of 300 sccm.) at 900 °C for 25 min, the iron precursor changed to iron nanoparticles as catalysts for the synthesis of CNTs at 1,005 °C. CH_4 and H_2 (CH_4 : H_2 = 1:2 by volume, with a total flow of 75 sccm.) were used as the carbon source, together with 0.43% H_2O for accelerating CNT growth. The growth time for the CNTs was about 30 min.

Characterization. The CNTs/CNTBs were inspected with a SEM (JSM 7401F, 1.0 kV), a Raman spectrometer (Horiba HR 800, 632.8 nm), and a TEM (JEM 2010, 120.0 kV). An optical microscope (long working distance metallography microscope, FS 70Z) and a supercontinuum laser were used for Resonance Rayleigh scattering. Another optical microscope (HIScope KH-3000, Hirox, Tokyo, Japan) was used for optical characterization and manipulation of CNTs/CNTBs.

2 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1a displays the schematic illustration of the synthesis of CNTBs by GFF during the normal growth process of CNTs (see Methods section for details). Gas barriers were used to guide the direction of the gas flow. As a consequence, the orientation of CNTs would focus and form the desired CNTBs. To facilitate the manipulation of CNT(B)s, mm-wide trenches were fabricated on a silicon substrate. With the assistance of TiO₂ inorganic nanoparticles, the direct visualization and manipulation of the CNT(B)s could be realized under an optical microscope (OM) (Figure 1b). Unlike those previously reported Y-shaped bundles typically consisting of not more than four CNTs acquired in the course of the normal growth process, the size of as-synthesized CNTBs by GFF method could be made of up to fifteen CNTs with length up to centimeters. The spherical aberration–corrected transmission electron microscopy (Cs-corrected TEM) characterization, illustrated in Figure 1c, reveals that the CNTBs were mainly formed from few-walled CNTs.

Figure 1. Fabrication and structural characterization of ultralong CNTs/CNTBs. (a) Schematic illustration of the in-situ fabrication of CNTBs via gas flow focusing (GFF) method. (b) Optical image of a suspended CNTB decorated with TiO₂ nanoparticles under an optical microscope. (c) The spherical aberration-corrected transmission electron microscopy (Cs-corrected TEM) characterization of the as-grown ultralong CNTs triple walls.

Raman spectroscopy is employed to investigate the structure of the CNTBs and their components. Generally, for the Raman spectra of single CNTs, there are two frequency feature components in the G-band: the upper frequency component (ω_G^+ , associated with vibrations along the direction of the CNT axis) and the lower frequency component (ω_G^- , associated with vibrations along the circumferential direction). It has been proven that the upper frequency component (ω_G^+) has a downshift to the lower frequency with the axial strain

increase in a single CNT. Besides, it is also found that the shift of ω_G^+ will also cause the shift of ω_G^- in the same direction. Thus, both the ω_G^+ and the ω_G^- will have a downshift to the lower frequency when there is a tensile axial strain in a suspended CNT. As shown in Figure 2a and b, it is evident that with the increase of the tensile strain in a CNTB-2, both the ω_G^+ and the ω_G^- have an obvious and continuous downshift with a rate of -8.8 and -7.8 $\text{cm}^{-1}/\% \text{strain}$, respectively, which is consistent with the previous reports of G-band downshift rate ranging from -6.2 to -23.6 $\text{cm}^{-1}/\% \text{strain}$, or ranging from -8.0 to -9.0 $\text{cm}^{-1}/\% \text{strain}$. In addition, when a suspended CNT with initial strain is broken, both the ω_G^+ and the ω_G^- have an obvious upshift to the high frequency due to the release of the tensile strains (Figure 2c). For a suspended CNTB-4 shown in Figure 2d, the wide G-band frequency distribution for the four components in the CNTB-4 clearly shows that they have different initial strains, which is the principal reason for the remarkable decrease of the tensile strength of CNTBs in comparison with that of single CNTs. For a CNTB consisting of CNTs with different initial strains, the components will break almost one by one under a tensile loading because they can't bear the loading synchronously and equally. Consequently, the overall tensile strength of the bundle will be impaired.

Figure 2. Raman spectra of the as-synthesized ultralong CNT(B)s. (a) G band shift of a suspended CNTB-2 at strains of 0, 1.1, 2.6, and 3.7%. (b) G band frequencies plotted as a function of applied strain. (c) G-band comparison of a suspended CNT before and after breaking. (d) G band of a CNTB-4 shown in the inset. Inset: Illustration for the Raman laser focused on the suspended CNTB-4. The broad multi-peak G band indicates the nonuniformity of the initial strains of the components in the CNTB-4.

9 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, centimeters-long CNTBs consisting of ultralong, continuous, defect-free, neat and well-aligned CNTs are in-situ synthesized using a GFF method. For as-grown horizontal CNT(B)s, we find that there is always an initial stress existed but few studies focus

on it. Resonance Raman spectroscopy was used to assess the initial stress of the ultralong carbon nanotubes as inorganic nanoparticles show no influence. It is concluded that the values of the initial stress exist in a pretty wide range and even in a bundle. This can have a big impact on the mechanical properties of ultralong carbon nanotube assemblies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No. 21636005), the Foundation for the National Basic Research Program of China (Grant No. 2016YFA0200102), the NSFC (Grant No. 11227202, 1147215) and the National Basic Research Program of China (Grant Nos. 2013CB934203).

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